

HORIZON 2020

Coordination and Support Action

Grant Agreement No: 652641

CONNECTING SCIENCE WITH SOCIETY

Deliverable 4.12

Second progress report on dissemination activities

Submission of Deliverable

Work Package	WP4
Deliverable no. & title	D 4.12 Second progress report on dissemination activities
Version	final
Creation Date	19 February 2018
Last change	09 March 2018
Status	<input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WP lead accepted <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Executive Board accepted
Dissemination level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU-Public <input type="checkbox"/> PP- Restricted to programme partners <input type="checkbox"/> RE- Restricted to a group specified by the consortium <input type="checkbox"/> CO- Confidential, only for members of the consortium
Lead Beneficiary	CNR-DTA (partner 4)
Contributors	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 1 – AWI, <input type="checkbox"/> 2 – CNRS, <input type="checkbox"/> 3 - NERC-BAS, <input type="checkbox"/> 4 - CNR-DTA, <input type="checkbox"/> 5 – SPRS, <input type="checkbox"/> 6 – IPEV, <input type="checkbox"/> 7 - IGOT-UL, <input type="checkbox"/> 8 – RUG, <input type="checkbox"/> 9 - RCN, <input type="checkbox"/> 10 – MINECO, <input type="checkbox"/> 11 – CSIC, <input type="checkbox"/> 12 - UW-APRI, <input type="checkbox"/> 13 – BAI, <input type="checkbox"/> 14 – GEUS, <input type="checkbox"/> 15 – VUB, <input type="checkbox"/> 16 – UOULU, <input type="checkbox"/> 17 – RBINS, <input type="checkbox"/> 18 - IGF PAS, <input type="checkbox"/> 19 - IG-TUT, <input type="checkbox"/> 20 – AMAP, <input type="checkbox"/> 21 – WOC, <input type="checkbox"/> 22 - GINR
Due date	28 February 2018
Delivery date	09 March 2018

1. Introduction

In its second reporting period (October 2016 – February 2018) EU-PolarNet's main dissemination efforts shifted its focus, from primarily raising awareness about the project (focus of the first reporting period) towards targeting outreach towards specific audiences and keeping affiliated partners and stakeholders regularly informed about project activities and results. As outlined in the Deliverable 4.2 "Integrated pan-European communication and engagement delivery plan" key stakeholders, and thus important audiences for EU-PolarNet's dissemination efforts are:

- Research communities - from institutions, universities and national polar operators
- Parliamentary and policy - European Commission, the European Parliament; national governments within member states
- Business and Industry sectors - such as shipping, oil, gas, fisheries and tourism;
- European public - including young people;
- Local Arctic communities; indigenous communities
- Polar organisations including IASC, SCAR, IASSA, Arctic Council, Antarctic Treaty Secretariat etc.;
- NGOs
- International networks and agencies such as the Council of Managers of National Antarctic Programmes (COMNAP); the Forum of Arctic Research Operators (FARO), INTERACT
- Media

In the following, EU-PolarNet's dissemination activities at conferences and events, online outreach (including the EU-PolarNet website, social media channels and email newsletter), media relations, outreach materials and scientific publications will be presented, as well as its coordinated outreach efforts within the EU Arctic Cluster.

Please note that this deliverable focussed on the dissemination aspect of activities in the understanding of the European Commission, as public disclosure of the results of the project in any medium. Communication activities, which include a two-way exchange of information, are evaluated in D2.4 "First progress report on science - stakeholder Interaction".

2. Dissemination at conferences and events

EU-PolarNet consortium members have actively promoted the work of the project at almost 50 national, European and international conferences and workshops during the past one and a half years (see Appendix 1). In addition to presenting the objectives and advances of the consortium at external events, distributing promotional materials and representing the project at panel discussions, members have also organised sessions and side events at a range of conferences, which were targeted both at a scientific audience and stakeholders.

For major sessions and side events organised by EU-PolarNet, the consortium has created written reports, which are publically available on the EU-PolarNet website and are targeted towards anyone interested to learn more about the discussion outcomes.

Available event reports

Event/Session title	Location	Date	Link to reports
"Stakeholder Workshop on Research Needs on Climate-related effects on the Arctic Cryosphere and Adaptation Options"	Arctic Science: Bringing Knowledge to Action Conference in Reston (Virginia) USA	April 2017	Link to full report
"Stakeholder engagement: moving from quantity to more quality"; and "Incorporation of Social Science and Humanities in large EU projects"	Ninth International Congress of Arctic Social Sciences in Umeå, Sweden	June 2017	Link to full report
"Breaking records: How high temperatures in the Arctic affect European society"	Brussels, Belgium	June 2017	Link to full report and presentations
"EU Arctic Policy: Science as catalyst for international cooperation"	Arctic Circle Assembly in Reykjavik, Iceland	October 2017	Link to full report
"Arctic States and Small Island States: Two regions inextricably linked through climate change"	UN Climate Conference COP23 in Bonn, Germany	November 2017	Link to full report
"Polar insights for climate action: Arctic science contributions to implementing the Paris Agreement"	UN Climate Conference COP23 in Bonn, Germany	November 2017	Link to full report

3. Online dissemination

3.1 The EU-PolarNet Website

The EU-PolarNet website (www.eu-polar.net) acts as one of the main online dissemination platforms for raising awareness about the project, sharing information related to the work of the consortium or affiliated projects and cooperation partners, and promoting upcoming events. The targeted audience ranges from the general public, to national and international policy makers, representatives from the industry, NGOs, interest groups and the wider science community. To meet the interest and needs of the various audience segments, the website offers both a wide range of informational static content and regularly updated contents, such as announcements and news.

The website also contains an internal part, which consortium members can log into, in order to retrieve consortium internal information and documents.

Since its launch the EU-PolarNet website has been visited 21.400 times with a large geographical coverage (Figure 1). Website visits are tracked with the analytical tool PIWIK.

Figure 1: Website visitors worldwide from April 2015 – January 2018

3.2 Social Media

Facebook

EU-PolarNet uses its [Facebook public group](#) to share news, events and calls with its ca. 350 members. Any member can post content, once it has been approved by the group moderators. The main audience are researchers of all disciplines with a focus on early career scientists.

Twitter

The EU-PolarNet [Twitter channel](#) (@EUPolarNet) serves as a platform to both share news, events and calls, but also to report live from conferences and workshops, giving people digitally access to discussions. Currently 1150 people follow @EUPolarNet.

LinkedIn

The EU-PolarNet [LinkedIn group](#) is used to share surveys and job postings from partnering institutions. It currently has close to 80 members.

YouTube

EU-PolarNet's [Youtube channel](#) features interviews with EU-PolarNet consortium members, in order to give the project and its participants a face. Furthermore event recordings and event trailers are available on the channel. Currently 30 people have subscribed and 27 videos are available.

Website referral

The social media channels serve as tools to refer people to the EU-PolarNet website for more detailed information about the project's results and activities (Figure 2). Facebook and Twitter thereby attract most visitors, while LinkedIn plays a subordinate role and YouTube is not relevant for EU-PolarNet website referrals.

Figure2: Referral to EU-PolarNet website from social media channels.

3.3 Newsletter

A quarterly EU-PolarNet newsletter informs recipients about news from the consortium and affiliated projects, reports about project results, reflects on developments in European polar research, introduces individual European polar research communities and gives a glimpse of conferences and events coming up in near future. In the second reporting period 7 issues, including seasonal greetings, have been sent out to more than 500 recipients. The newsletter is further more shared by consortium members and affiliated partners with their national polar community. EU-PolarNet also regularly writes contributions to the IASSA Northern Notes newsletter.

4. Outreach materials

The BAS media team has created a range of outreach materials for the project's launch, which are still regularly used. These materials include an EU-PolarNet flyer, which has been distributed and set up during various conferences and workshops, a roll-up and a poster. Furthermore USB-Hubs were created, which carried the slogan "Connecting Science with Society", as giveaways at conferences and workshops.

5. Media

In the second reporting period, EU-PolarNet reached out to the general media to promote two high level sessions the consortium co-organised during the UN Climate Conference COP23 in Bonn, Germany. Furthermore, EU-PolarNet's former Coordinator, Karin Lochte, was featured in an interview conducted by the German Ministry for Education and Science about female scientists in Horizon2020 projects ([link to interview](#)). EU-PolarNet was also mentioned by Commissioner Karmenu Vella during the Press Conference "A sustainable Arctic – innovative approaches" in Oulu, Finland. He uses the consortium as an example for international science cooperation: "And fostering cooperation between scientists – like the 22 European research institutes that make up the EU-PolarNet initiative, the largest pool of expertise for polar research" ([link to statement](#)).

6. Scientific publications

Through its increasing engagement with stakeholders, EU-PolarNet has gained valuable insights to how stakeholders would like to get engaged in science projects and where they see research priorities that are of immediate relevance to them. This information is in the process of getting evaluated scientifically and the results to be submitted to scientific journals. The first article was submitted to a *Polar Record* special issue on education, outreach & engagement in January 2018. It is titled "Tell us how to engage you! Asking stakeholders about their engagement preferences" and gives insights to a stakeholder engagement survey EU-PolarNet conducted.

7. EU Arctic Cluster

Besides disseminating EU-PolarNet results and information, the consortium also initiated joint outreach activities with the so call EU Arctic Cluster. The EU Arctic Cluster is a network of 7 currently funded Horizon 2020 projects (EU-PolarNet, APPLICATE, ARICE, Blue-Action, INTAROS, INTERACT and Nunataryuk) and the Framework Programme 7 funded project ICE-ARC. Its objective is to create synergies between the projects and enhance capacities and resources through joint actions. To coordinate these Cluster activities three task groups have been set up, of which one focusses on communication and dissemination. First dissemination actions of the EU Arctic Cluster included a booth at the Arctic Circle Assembly 2017 in Reykjavik, Iceland, a flyer, and a side event at the UN Climate Conference COP23 in Bonn, Germany. Furthermore EU-PolarNet hosts an EU Arctic Cluster page on its website, which currently serves as the Cluster's main web presence.

APPENDIX 1

EU-PolarNet dissemination activities at conferences, events and workshops

Title of event	Location	Date (year/month)	WP affiliation	objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet project	information material distributed	Type of audience (put x for all relevant)						
						scientific community	industry	civil society	policy makers	medias	indigenous peoples	other (specify)
YOPP Arctic Observations meeting	Reading, UK	2016/09	WP2, WP3, WP4	Attendance as EU-PolarNet representative								
Arctic Circle 2016	Reykjavik, Iceland	2016/10	WP1, WP4	Organisation of Breakout Session and Booth	Flyers	x	x	x	x	x		
ARCA - Arctic: present Climatic change and pAst extreme events	Rome, Italy	2016/10	WP1, WP2, WP4	Presenting EU-PolarNet		x			x			
COP22	Marrakesh, Morocco	2016/11	WP1, WP4	Organisation of Side Event	Flyers	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Interoperability Workshop and Assessment Process	Frascati, Italy	2016/11	WP2, WP3, WP4	Attendance as EU-PolarNet representative		x						
Polar Forum 2016	Stockholm, Sweden	2016/11	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4	National dissemination on activities in EU-PolarNet		x			x			
ArcticNet Annual Conference	Winnipeg, Canada	2016/12	WP1	Speaker on behalf of EU-PolarNet		x						
WOC Sustainable Ocean Summit	Rotterdam, Netherlands	2016/12	WP2, WP4	Presentation and panellist in Breakout Session		x	x					
Arctic Science Ministerial Workshop	Arlington, USA	2017/01	WP1, WP4	Invited Participant		x			x		x	
Blue Action Kick-Off	Berlin, Germany	2017/01	WP1	Presenting EU-PolarNet		x	x					
IASC	Iceland	2017/01	wp2	Presenting EU-PolarNet	Flyers	x					x	
APPLICATE General Assembly 2017	Bremerhaven, Germany	2017/02	WP1, WP4	Presenting EU-PolarNet	Flyers	x	x					
Arctic Science Summit Week 2017	Prag, Czech Republic	2017/03	WP1, WP4	EU-PolarNet Presentation in APECS session and poster about EU-PolarNet white paper process	Flyers	x	x		x		x	
EU-PolarNet General Assembly	Prag, Czech Republic	2017/03	WP1, WP4	Reporting about project status	Flyers	x	x		x			
European Maritime Capabilities in the Arctic Meeting	Brussels, Belgium	2017/03	WP1, WP4	Presenting EU-PolarNet								military
Transatlantic Cooperation Meeting	Brussels, Belgium	2017/03	WP1	Invited Participant		x			x			
AMAP Conference: Arctic Science: Bringing Knowledge to Action	Reston, USA	2017/04	WP4	Attendance as EU-PolarNet representative		x	x	x	x	x		
AMAP-EU-PolarNet Stakeholder Workshop on Research Needs on Climate-related effects on the Arctic Cryosphere and Adaptation Options	Reston, USA	2017/04	WP1, WP4	Organisation of stakeholder workshop	Flyers	x	x	x	x			
Arctic Council Finnish Chairmanship Event	Berlin, Germany	2017/05	WP1, WP4	Attendance as EU-PolarNet representative		x	x	x	x	x	x	
Arctic Dialogue	Berlin, Germany	2017/05	WP1, WP4	Attendance as EU-PolarNet representative		x			x			
INTAROS Stakeholder Workshop	Brussels, Belgium	2017/05	WP1	Invited Participant		x			x			
A New Era of Blue Enlightenment	Lisbon, Portugal	2017/06	WP3	Attendance as EU-PolarNet representative	Flyers	x	x		x	x		
Ninth International Congress of Arctic Social Sciences	Umea, Sweden	2017/06	WP1, WP4	Organisation of two breakout session	Flyers	x					x	
Policy Briefing: Breaking records: How high temperatures in the Arctic affect European society	Brussels, Belgium	2017/06	WP1, WP4	Organisation of policy briefing	Flyers	x		x	x			
Sofia Science Festival 2017	Sofia, Bulgaria	2017/06	WP2, WP3, WP4	EU-PolarNet Presentation	Flyers	x		x		x		
Encontro Ciência 2017	Lisbon, Portugal	2017/07	WP3	Presented PROPOLAR with reference to EUPOLARNET								
2nd Asian Conference on Permafrost	Sapporo, Japan	2017/07	WP3	Attendance as EU-PolarNet representative	Flyers	x						
SCAR Biology Symposium	Leuven, Belgium	2017/07	WP1, WP4	Attendance as EU-PolarNet representative		x						
Knowledge contest and following expedition to North Scandinavia for Estonian high school students.	Tallinn, Estonia	2017/07	WP4	Informing about EU-PolarNet	Flyers	x		x		x		students
COMNAP Meeting	Brno, Czech Republic	2017/08	WP1, WP2, WP3	Attendance as EU-PolarNet representative		x						
meetin g meterologia FMI	Helsinki	2017/08	WP2, WP3, WP4	Attendance as EU-PolarNet representative								
APECS Bulgaria Open Conference	Sinemorets, Bulgaria	2017/09	WP2, WP3, WP4	EU-PolarNet Presentation in APECS Bulgaria symposium		x						
European Researchers Night 2017	Stara Zagora, Bulgaria	2017/09	WP2, WP3, WP4	EU-PolarNet Presentation	Flyers	x		x		x		

Sustainable Development Group (Arctic Council)	Inari, Finland	2017/09 WP2, WP4	short up-date of the EU-PolarNet project and the relevance for the SDWG.						x		x
Arctic Circle 2017	Reykjavik, Iceland	2017/10 WP1, WP4	Organisation of Breakout Session and Booth	Flyers, USB Hubs	x	x	x	x		x	
8th Conference on Portuguese polar Science	Covilhã, Portugal	2017/11 WP3	Attendance as EU-PolarNet representative	Flyers	x						
COP23	Bonn, Germany	2017/11 WP1, WP4	Organisation of 3 side events	Flyers	x	x	x	x		x	x
Imobar workshop	Bruxelles	2017/11 WP2, WP3, WP4	Invited Participant								
North American Roundtable Event at Norwegian Embassy	Berlin, Germany	2017/11 WP1	Invited Participant		x				x		
Developments in the Arctic Today and Tomorrow: Risks and Opportunities	Tallinn, Estonia	2017/11 WP4	Informing about EU-PolarNet	Flyers	x		x	x		x	
Polar Forum 2017	Stockholm, Sweden	2016/11 WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4	National dissemination on activities in EU-PolarNet		x				x		
Arctic Change 2017	Québec, Canada	2017/12 WP3	Attendance as EU-PolarNet representative		x	x			x	x	x
Arctic Change Conference	Quebec, Canada	2017/12 WP1, WP4	Presented EU-PolarNet within the EU Arctic Cluster		x				x		x
Human rights and Arctic	Helsinki, Finland	2017/09 WP2, WP4	Invited participant	Flyers	x	x	x	x		x	x
APPLICATE General Assembly 2018	Barcelona, Spain	2018/01 WP1	Presented EU-PolarNet within the EU Arctic Cluster		x						
Arctic Frontiers 2018	Tromso, Norway	2018/01 WP1, WP4	Organisation of stakeholder workshop and EU Arctic Cluster presentation	Flyers	x	x	x	x		x	x
INTAROS General Assembly	Helsinki, Finland	2018/01 WP1, WP4	Presented EU-PolarNet within the EU Arctic Cluster	Flyers	x	x					
ARICE Kick off	Bremerhaven, Germany	2018/02 WP1, WP4	Presented EU-PolarNet within the EU Arctic Cluster	Flyers	x	x					polar operators